

VASEACAD

Sustainable Blue
Economy Partnership

Funded by
the European Union

Background

From Waste to Resource: Unlocking the Value of Aquaculture and Fisheries Side Streams

The aquaculture and fisheries sectors produce significant amounts of by-products, residual biomass, and discarded materials such as heads, skins, backbones, and viscera. These discards make up 25% to 70% of raw materials and are often underutilised or disposed of as waste. This practice leads to inefficient use of valuable marine resources and results in unnecessary emissions, environmental harm, and economic losses.

VASEACAD is an innovative project that aims at transforming underutilised marine side streams into bioactive protein hydrolysates and high-value biomolecules, as well as developing novel fish feed ingredients through innovative inter-species recycling approaches. By unlocking the potential of marine by-products via advanced bioprocessing, VASEACAD promotes circularity, reduces waste and emissions, and enhances Europe's blue bioeconomy.

The Challenge

VASEACAD tackles the challenge of fragmented biomass in Mediterranean fisheries by enabling on-site, small-scale processing, through SINTEF's Mobile Sealab. The project accelerates the journey from lab to market, scaling production of hydrolysates and creating designer ingredients with tailored bioactivity. By valorising marine resources, reducing waste and promoting inter-species recycling, VASEACAD strengthens Europe's blue bioeconomy and contributes to a more sustainable, climate-resilient aquaculture sector.

The Solution

VASEACAD leverages advanced bioprocessing techniques to transform by-products from bluefin tuna, European seabass, gilthead seabream, European sprat, and blue whiting into bioactive protein hydrolysates, functional fish proteins, and high-quality oils. These products are designed to enhance human health by addressing inflammation and age-related conditions and promoting muscle and skin wellness.

VASEACAD also aims to strengthen the resilience and sustainability of aquafeeds, thereby contributing to a more circular economy and promoting sustainable aquaculture.

The VASEACAD involves key sea basins such as the Mediterranean, Black Sea, and Atlantic, with activities led by partners from Greece, Ireland, Malta, Norway, Cyprus, Spain, and Türkiye.

Key Messages

- Turning fish waste into valuable products

- Supporting health through marine bioactive compounds

- Advancing circular and sustainable aquaculture

- Scaling innovation from lab to industry

- Boosting coastal economies and resilience

- Reducing environmental impact and supporting EU goals

VASEACAD

Partners:

Funders:

vaseacad.eu

Coordinator:

Dr. Yannis Kotzamanis
Hellenic Centre for Marine
Research,
Greece

Contact jokotz@hcmr.gr

Endorsed by:

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